

Original article

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BUSINESS ANALYSIS OF META PLATFORM IN POST COVID-19 TIME

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Abstract: *Meta is the largest social network globally in terms of the number of active users. It has built an ecosystem with all the characteristics of a modern monopoly. This paper aims to investigate and analyse the business results of the platform during the pandemic period and after the end of the COVID-19 pandemic. The research used data that the corporation publishes in the form of the Meta Annual Report, which serves investors for business on the stock exchange. The research includes the analysis of selected financial parameters, and the analysis of user trends to determine the stability of the network effect on the platform. In the analysis, a statistical trend regression model is used to determine the business result in the selected time period. The research results proved that the COVID-19 pandemic did not have a significant impact on the overall business results. The corporation entered the process of reorganization and expansion of business activities after the end of the pandemic, which had a positive effect on the financial result.*

Keywords: *digital transformation, Facebook, Meta, platform economy, social media.*